

How to improve Elasticsearch with deeplearning

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Elasticsearch could be used to index huge of documents crawling the web. When a user put a full text query he has no idea about indices contents. The principals question is which terms he should put or use in the query

2. Aim

Improve the relevance of Elasticsearch by auto-generating clusters of terms having some relations between them.

3. Material and methods

We make the POC with a corpus of document having a size of about one terra byte. The corpus is composed of multilingual documents crawled form many social media resources. Clusters of related terms are generated from the corpus using deep-learning technics (word2vec). Those clusters are stored into a comma separated file and declared in Elasticsearch as a synonym file and will be use by the system when analyzing the queries.

4. Results

The quality of the system is improved by about 10 percent. But we should make a trade of between precision and recall by adjusting the size of the term clusters. This size is fixed in advance and passed as a parameter to the Deep-learning algorithm. We do not use synonyms in the indexing phase because doing that we increase the size of indices by about 20 times and may be more.

To have good association between terms of the same cluster we must use a huge database (or corpus). One terra byte is a minimum size. More we have documents better we obtain good precision.

5. Conclusions

We must make tests about using syntactic and lexical relationships between terms.

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6. Keywords

Elasticsearch, deeplearning, indexing, recall, precision, document relevance

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